

Impact of Finley-Jensen Problem Solving Model on Retention in Algebraic Concepts among Students in Public Polytechnics, North West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigates the Impact of Finley-Jensen problem solving model on retention in algebraic concepts among students in public polytechnics, North West Nigeria. A pretest, post-tests and post-post-test Quasi-experimental research design was used for the study. Fourteen public polytechnics made up the population of the Study with a sample size of 6,985 national diploma one (ND I) students during the 2021/2022 academic session. Two schools were randomly selected as population Samples. The experimental and control groups were exposed to Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving model and Lecture Method respectively. The experimental group was taught algebra (MTH 112) using Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving model while the control group was taught MTH 112 using Lecture method. Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT) was designed by the researchers for data collection. The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT) was determined to be 0.76 using Cronbach alpha at $\alpha = 0,05$ significance level. There was significant difference in the mean scores of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley – Jensen problem model and their counterpart taught using conventional lecture method. The finding revealed that students that were taught using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model retained better than those exposed to Lecture method. Teachers (Lecturers) were advised to integrate Finley-Jensen problem-solving model in their pedagogy

Keyword: Algebra, Finley-Jensen, Problem Solving and Retention

Introduction

Mathematics is essential to national prosperity in providing tools for understanding science, engineering, technology and economics. It is essential in public decision-making and for partaking in the knowledge economy. Mathematics equips pupils/students with uniquely powerful ways to describe, analyze and change the world. It can stimulate moments of pleasure and wonder for all pupils/students when they solve a problem for the first time, discover a more stylish solution, or notice hidden connections. Pupils/students who are functional in mathematics are able to think independently in applied and abstract ways, and can reason, solve problems and assess risk (Tudunkaya & Jamilu, 2019). The need of mathematics in human life can not be over emphasize. According to National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2000) mathematics is regard to as a cultural heritage for science and technological community. As part of the National Board for Technical Education Curriculum, algebra is a core course for all sciences, engineering and environmental technology. Algebra is one of the studied areas of mathematics that deals with the representation of problems or situations in the form of mathematical expressions. All the branches of mathematics needs algebra. The study of algebra starts with solving of equations such as polynomials equations. Algebra and elementary trigonometry is almost a general course to all students of sciences, engineering technology, environmental technology and even in some management courses. Knowing the importance of mathematics in human life, then the learning of mathematics needs to be well prepared. For effective learning to be efficiently taken, we need the right approaches and methods. For effective learning, the teaching activities should centred on students activities (Overy, 2011). These activities include problem-solving strategy which improve student attendance and attitude toward learning, by making them to have mastery of the concepts and skills.

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The Finley-Jensen problem solving model (1996) is based on Dewey (1933) and Bruner (1973) theories of learning. These scholars have agreed that meaningful learning can only be achieved through active participation of learners. Farooq (1980) points out that a “problem” usually indicates a challenge, the meeting of which requires study and investigation. Skinner (1984) states that the term “problem-solving” is defined as the frame work or pattern within which creative thinking and learning takes place. It is a process of overcoming difficulties that appear to interfere with the attainment of a goal. Polya (1945) defines problem-solving as the process used to solve a problem that does not have an obvious solution. Bay (2000) explains teaching about problem-solving as the teaching of strategies, or heuristics, in order to solve problems. Despite the applications of mathematics in science and technology, students retention ability use to be very poor at the end of semester examination.

Retention as defined by Yero (2011) is the ability of a learner to recall, remember and recollect a body of Knowledge after passing through instruction. According to Chauchan in Neboh (2012) retention is direct correlate of positive transfer of learning. For students’ retention, Umar (2011) observed that students’ experience is a significant factor in retention and that the strategies of improving retention rate can be adopted by the teacher. Bichi, (2002) opined that anything which aids meaningful learning improves students’ retention and while things that lead to interference among learned materials decrease the speed and efficiency of learning and accelerates forgoing. Idris (2014) observed that, retention is the ability to keep and consequently remember things or materials experienced or learned at a later time. Chibabi, *et al* (2018) in their study found that teaching methods play a great impact in secondary school students retention especially in science related subjects. Retention is imperative in any academic activity. Low academic performance as well as retention amongst students in Sciences seems to be as a result of use of teacher’s-centred method which lead to poor academic retention. Many researches had carried out to improve the students’ retention abilities.

Gloria (2020), investigated the Effects of Problem Solving Strategy on Retention in Reading comprehension, the study reveals that there was a significant difference in the retention of students taught reading comprehension with problem-solving strategy and that of those taught same contents with the conventional read, reread method. Many studies were also carried out to investigate the effect of problem – solving strategy on student retention ability and there results shows that there is a significant difference in retention ability of students taught using problem-solving compare to those taught with lecture method. Charles, *et al* (2021), studied the Effectiveness of Learning Activity Package Instructional Strategy on secondary school student’s retention in chemistry, it was shown that chemistry students that were taught Basic Chemistry using Learning Activity Package recorded higher Retention than those taught with lecture method.

Obochi (2018), investigated the impact of Problem-solving strategy on retention and academic performance in biology among low ability secondary school students in Zaria, Kaduna State Nigeria. Jamilu *et al* (2023) investigated the Impact of Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving Model on Performance and Retention in 3-D Geometry among SSII Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. It was revealed that Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving Model enhances the Performance and Retention of Secondary School Students on 3-D Geometry concepts. Mukhar *et al.* (2021), studied the effects of Jigsaw IV Cooperative Learning Strategy (J4CLS) on students’ retention in Geometry among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis. It was shown that, the Students that were exposed to J4CLS had retained geometrical concepts compare to those that were taught using the conventional teaching method. Still poor retention ability among national diploma I students has become a challenging problem to educators in our institutions, more especially in mathematics which lead to poor performance at the end of semester examinations which may be as a result of conventional lecture method used for teaching in them. This paper attempts to investigate the impact of Finley-Jensen problem solving model on retention in algebraic concepts among students in public polytechnics, North West Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

To examine the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concept using Finley-Jensen Problem-Solving model and those expose to lecture method.

Research Questions:

Is there any significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Null Hypotheses:

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0,05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

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Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test-post-test and post posttest non-equivalent control group design. The essence of pre-test was to determine the academic equivalence of the two groups before the treatment while post-posttest was to determine the performance of the student after the treatment. The students in the experimental group were exposed to algebraic concepts through problem solving model for a period of eight (8) weeks and the control group were taught the same concepts using conventional lecture method after which post-test was administered to both groups. The population of the study comprised of public polytechnics in north-west zone of Nigeria. There are fourteen public polytechnics in North-West with the total number, of 6,985 NDI students taking algebra (MTH 112) as at the time the data was collected. For the purpose of this study a simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample institutions. The instrument for this study is Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT). The reliability coefficient of Algebraic Achievement Test (AAT) was determined to be 0.76. For the purpose of generating and analysing data AAT comprises ten (10) essay test questions were developed for the study, which allowed the students to write their understanding on the algebraic concepts.

Results

The result of the analysis was used to answer the research question using descriptive statistics while inferential statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at alpha (α) = 0.05 level significance.

Research Question 1

Is there any significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation for Retention ability

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Experimental	22.93	5.31
2.	Control	12.73	4.09

(Field work, 2023)

The results in table 1 shows that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 22.93 retained higher than their counterparts in the control group with a mean score of 12.73. This shows that Finley-Jensen enhances students' retention ability.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Table 2: T-test on students' retention ability of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	SD	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	df	Remark
Experimental	117	22.88	5.31	18.07	1.65	223	S
Control	108	12.73	4.09				

S=significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2 shows that the mean scores of post posttest for both the experimental and control groups with the mean of 22.88 and 12.88 respectively. The hypothesis says "there is no significant difference between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method". But from the table above we have $t_{critical} (18.07) > t_{calculated} (1.65)$ at $\alpha=0.05$ significant level. Thus, H_{01} is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

Results of testing null hypothesis shows that significant difference exist between the mean retention score of students taught algebraic concepts using Finley-Jensen problem-solving model and those exposed to lecture teaching method. The analysis of the hypothesis showed that the use of Finley-Jensen problem solving model lead to higher retention than the

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traditional method of teaching. The result of the mean scores of the student in the experimental group maintained a higher retention rates than their counterparts in the control group (see table 1). The nature of Finley-Jensen problem-solving model is learning by doing and elaborating. In Finley-Jensen problem-solving model the students worked individually and later discuss their finding in pairs, where each student developed self confidence in the topic taught. The consistent elaboration of MTH 112 concepts at Finley-Jensen problem-solving model provides students who either received the explanation or those who gave the explanation with a deep understanding and a more complete retention of the concepts being learnt for a longer period of time. The post post test was administered after two weeks and the result was showed in table 1. This finding agrees with the findings of Charles *et al* (2021), Obochi (2018), Mukhtar *et al* (2021) and Gloria (2020) who found that there is significant difference on retention abilities on students that are exposed to problem solving than those in control group, taught the concepts using traditional method. This is because problem-Solving in general and specifically Finely-Jensen problem-solving model encourages verbalization and made students communicate their ideas very well to classmates.

Conclusion

The paper study the impact of Finley-Jensen problem solving model on retention in algebraic concepts among students in public polytechnics, North West Nigeria. It was shown that better retention ability was achieved when using Finley – Jensen problem solving model in teaching algebraic concept (MTH 112) among national diploma one students compared to normal conventional lecture method

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend that: Lectures (teachers) should incorporate Finley – Jensen problem solving model in teaching Mathematics more especially at ND level.

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